

Thiodiazines.

Part IV.

BY

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Derivatives of thiol-thiodiazine are readily obtained by the condensation of benzyl- and nitrobenzyl-dithiocarbazines with α -halogenated esters in presence of a suitable condensing agent (Bose, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 148).

The investigation of thiodiazines has now been continued by studying the condensation of esters of phenyldithiocarbazine with ω -bromoacetophenone and with *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone. This leads to the production of substances that show *cis*- and *trans*-isomerism and that can be converted into thiol-thiodiazines.

In alcoholic solution, alkyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazines and ω -bromoacetophenone reacted so as to give rise to uncrystallisable oils, the formation of which was traced to the influence of hydrobromic acid liberated in the reaction. For, if the hydrobromic acid is neutralised as soon as it is formed or if the condensation proceeds in presence of the calculated amount of alkali, crystalline products of condensation, having the composition $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{N} : \text{C}(\text{SAlk}) \cdot \text{S}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$, are obtained in good yield. The course of the reaction, however, was found to be greatly influenced by the method of neutralising hydrobromic acid. Thus when an alcoholic solution of a mixture of methyl-phenyldithiocarbazine and

ω -bromoacetophenone was treated with the calculated quantity of alcoholic potash at the ordinary temperature, a bright yellow crystalline product, m. p. 100° , was obtained. If, however, an alcoholic solution of ω -bromoacetophenone is added to a mixture of equimolecular quantities of the ester and alcoholic potash, the condensation product consists of pale yellow soft needles, m. p. 93° . The two products are isomeric. Such isomerides have also been obtained with ethyl- and *n*-propyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazines on the one hand and ω -bromoacetophenone and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone on the other.

The compounds, obtained by the first method, are brittle, deep yellow crystalline substances having, as a rule, higher melting points than the corresponding isomerides. They are further characterised by their sparing solubility in ligroin, by their capacity to yield phenylhydrazones, and their stability.

The isomeric compounds, obtained by the other method, are soft pale yellow crystalline substances, which are extremely soluble in most organic media and are even easily soluble in ligroin. Moreover, they fail to yield phenylhydrazones under the conditions employed for their isomerides and are unstable.

Hantzsch and Werner's theory of the spatial arrangement of atoms or groups about the system $>C=N-$ has been applied to the mono- and the di-alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazines. It was found that aldehydes condense with the mono-alkyl compound to give thiodiazoles, thus:

These mono-alkyl compounds were, therefore, regarded as having the thiol group in the *cis*-position relative to the anilino group (*cis*-thiol configuration).

From these mono-alkyl compounds, by the action of alkyl iodide, Busch was able to obtain dialkyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazines of the type $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{N} : \text{C}(\text{SR})(\text{SR}')$.

(Busch, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1119; Busch and Kraft, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1911, [ii] 84, 293.) Thus there are two isomerides of the type $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{N}=\text{C}(\text{SR})(\text{SR}')$: the second alkyl group that is introduced occupies the *cis*-position with respect to the anilino group.

But it has already been stated that the isomerides of phenacyl and of *p*-methylphenacyl-alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazine can be obtained from the same components under different conditions of experiment. Evidently the suggestion of Busch (*loc. cit.*) that mono-alkyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazines react in the *cis*-thiol form only cannot be maintained in its entirety. The present author has, however, reasons to believe that the configurations given by Busch to his alkyl derivatives of phenyldithiocarbazine are correct. On this analogy the pale yellow compounds, referred to above, would receive the formula (II). Consequently the bright yellow isomerides of higher melting point would be represented by (I), that is, by *trans*-configuration.

These assumptions receive indirect support from the melting points of the different isomerides as also from

their stability and behaviour towards phenylhydrazine. As already mentioned, the bright yellow products, for which the formula (I) has been assumed, readily yielded phenylhydrazones when boiled with phenylhydrazine in alcohol-acetic acid solution. The isomerides (II) on the other hand failed to do so. The non-formation of phenylhydrazones in the latter case is not abnormal if we assume a mutual influence of the keto and anilino groups due to their spatial proximity.

Attempts were made to obtain definite proof of these structures by experiment. It followed from the constitution (II) given above to the lower-melting isomerides that they would be converted into thiodiazine derivatives by the elimination of a molecule of water thus :

The higher-melting isomerides, represented by (I), on the contrary, are incapable of undergoing such intramolecular condensations due to the unfavourable positions of the reactive groups in the molecule. In actual experiment it was found, however, that both the isomerides, when heated to 100° in alcoholic solution for four hours or when heated without any diluent at 140-45° for 10-15 minutes yielded (III) with elimination of water. This result in the case of the *trans*-compound can be explained only on the assumption that (I) changes into (II)* before undergoing the thiodiazine condensation.

* That such isomerides are interconvertible when kept in the fused state for some time has been observed by Busch. In the present case the transformation of (I) into (II) and *vice versa* could be observed in many cases under suitable experimental conditions (*vide* pp. 211-12).

The production of thiodiazines by these methods is therefore not reliable for indicating the difference in constitution between (I) and (II).

Having failed to obtain the desired results under the experimental conditions mentioned above, attention was directed to observing the rate of elimination of water from the isomerides under strictly comparable conditions. For this purpose the isomerides of $\text{Ph.NH.N} : \text{C}(\text{SEt}) \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{Ph}$ were dissolved in anhydrous benzene containing a little anhydrous copper sulphate in suspension and the mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature. It was expected that the copper sulphate would become blue much more quickly in the case of the *cis*-isomeride than in the other.

The compound, m. p. 87° , (for which a *cis*-structure has been assumed) gave after 48 hours a 45 per cent. yield of the corresponding thiodiazine. The development of the blue colour could not be observed as a portion decomposed into sulphuretted hydrogen thereby converting copper sulphate into cupric sulphide. The isomeride, m. p. 84° (for which a *trans*-configuration has been assumed), was found after the given period to have undergone partial isomeric change into the *cis*-compound. The copper sulphate in this case turned greyish but not blue. The thiodiazine was not formed at all even in the course of a week. This is certainly an unmistakable evidence in favour of the constitutions already proposed in the foregoing pages.

The thiodiazines can be obtained from either isomeride by the method already indicated. They may be directly obtained by boiling a mixture of the bromo-ketone and alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate in pyridine solution for a few minutes. The reaction, no doubt, proceeds with intermediate formation of the *cis*-compound. For it has been found that if the reaction in pyridine solution is

carried on at a low temperature a *cis*-compound is invariably obtained.

The *trans*-compounds, on the other hand, are also obtained when the reactants are boiled in alcoholic solution containing precipitated calcium carbonate in suspension. The function of the carbonate is to decompose the hydrobromic acid as soon as it is formed.

These reactions for the formation of *cis*-and *trans*-isomerides together with those mentioned in the beginning of the paper lead to the following conclusion.

An alkaline medium favours the formation of the *cis*-compound with the total exclusion of the *trans*-isomeride. A faintly acid medium, on the other hand, invariably yields the *trans*-compound.

The thiodiazines (III) are very stable substances with high melting points and form pale yellow, hard, transparent prisms or needles.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Methods of Preparation of Phenacyl-alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinates.

(i) Molecular proportions of alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate and ω -bromoacetophenone or *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone were dissolved in warm absolute alcohol, the solution rapidly cooled and one molecule of 10 per cent. alcoholic caustic potash or ammonia run in gradually with constant shaking. The precipitated potassium bromide was immediately filtered off. The filtrate deposited on standing yellow crystals which were purified by crystallisation from absolute alcohol. A rise of temperature during the reaction is undesirable as the yield is considerably diminished thereby.

(ii) Alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate (one mol.), the bromo-ketone (one mol.) and a large excess of precipitated

calcium carbonate (5-6 mols.) were heated in absolute alcoholic solution for 15-20 minutes, by which time the pungent smell of the bromo-ketone practically disappeared and the solution turned yellow. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on cooling yielded the dithioester in long bright yellow needles or plates which were found to be identical with the corresponding product obtained by the previous method.

These two methods yielded *trans*-phenacyl derivatives.

(iii). The alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate (1 mol.) was dissolved in alcoholic potash (1 mol. of 10 per cent.), the solution cooled and an alcoholic solution of one mol. of the bromo-ketone gradually added with constant shaking. The potassium bromide which had separated out, was immediately filtered off. The condensation product gradually separated from the filtrate in star-like aggregates which were collected after an hour, dried on porcelain and recrystallised from ligroin or dilute alcohol.

(iv). To a cold solution of the alkyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate (1 mol.) in pyridine, the solid bromo-ketone was added all at once and shaken thoroughly; the flask, in which the reaction was being carried out was kept cool. The reaction was completed within a few minutes. A large volume of water was then added when a brown oil was precipitated. The oil was dissolved in warm absolute alcohol. The alcoholic solution on standing for some time deposited pale yellow needles which were identical with the corresponding product obtained by method (iii).

The *cis*-compounds were formed by the last two reactions.

trans-Phenacyl-methyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate,

This compound was obtained by methods (i) and (ii). It crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow needles, m.p. 100°. It is extremely soluble in acetone, pyridine, chloroform and benzene and only sparingly soluble in light petroleum. The yield of the pure product amounted to about 80 per cent. of that required by theory. (Found: C=60.42; H=5.48. $C_{16}H_{16}ON_2S_2$ requires C=60.75; H=5.33 per cent.)

Phenylhydrazone.—The above ketone was heated in alcoholic solution under reflux for about 15 minutes with an excess of phenylhydrazine and a little acetic acid. The dark coloured solution was cooled, acidified with acetic acid and diluted with water when a brown oil separated. The oil solidified on being left overnight. After two crystallisations from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol it was obtained as colourless, hard prisms melting at 126.7°. The phenylhydrazone gradually turned brown on keeping. (Found: N=13.93. $C_{22}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires N=13.79 per cent.)

trans-Phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate, which was prepared like the preceding methyl derivative (90 per cent. yield), crystallised from hot alcohol in long, yellow needles, m. p. 82°. It is very soluble in acetone, carbon disulphide and pyridine but very sparingly in cold alcohol and hot ligroin. (Found: C=61.53; H=5.37; N=8.63. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2S_2$ requires C=61.81; H=5.45; N=8.48 per cent.)

The *phenylhydrazone*, obtained by the method already described, crystallised from dilute pyridine in transparent prismatic needles, m. p. 136°. (Found: N=13.41. $C_{23}H_{24}N_4S_2$ requires N=13.34 per cent.)

n-Propyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate.—A mixture of 2.7 gm. of caustic potash in 30 c. c. of rectified spirit and 5 gm. of phenylhydrazine was cooled to 0° and 5 gm. of carbon disulphide were dropped in with constant shaking.

n-Propyl iodide (7.5 gm.) was added. The mixture was well shaken for some time and allowed to stand for an hour at the room temperature. The solution was then acidified with a very dilute solution of acetic acid. The crystals were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from dilute alcohol. Yield 5 gm. It formed colourless needles, m. p. 125°, which gradually decomposed on keeping. It is very soluble in benzene, acetone, pyridine, hot alcohol and aqueous alkali. (Found: N=12.34. C₁₀H₁₄N₂S₂ requires N=12.39 per cent.)

trans-Phenacyl-*n*-propyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate

was obtained by method (ii). It could not be obtained by method (i). It is very soluble in acetone, benzene, and ether and was crystallised from a small quantity of alcohol in yellow shining plates, m. p. 56°. (Found: N=8.22. C₁₈H₂₀ON₂S₂ requires N=8.14 per cent.)

trans-Phenacyl-*benzyl*-phenyldithiocarbazinate could not be obtained either by method (i) or (ii).

trans-*p*-Methylphenacyl-*methyl*-phenyldithiocarbazinate, obtained by methods (i) and (ii) from equivalent quantities of *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone¹ and methylphenyldithiocarbazinate, crystallised from hot alcohol or

¹ *Preparation of p-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone.*—To 26.8 gms. of *p*-methylacetophenone dissolved in 120 gms. of glacial acetic acid were added 30 gms. of bromine dissolved in 40 c. c. of the same solvent. The mixture was well shaken and heated in a warm water-bath at 50-60° for a few minutes until the red colour of bromine had completely disappeared. A current of dry air was passed through the solution to drive off the hydrobromic acid and the solution was poured on 400 gms. of crushed ice. After three hours the crystalline solid was collected under suction and recrystallised from rectified spirit. The yield of pure product amounted to about 60 per cent. of that required by theory.

The above procedure, which is a modification of Kunckell's method (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 577), can be quickly carried out; the product is purer and the yield better (60 per cent. as compared with 15 per cent. obtained by Kunckell's method).

dilute acetone in yellow shining plates, m. p. 109-110°. It is very soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide and pyridine but only sparingly in ligroin, ether and cold alcohol. (Found: C=61.53; H=5.47. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2S_2$ requires C=61.81; H=5.45 per cent.)

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from absolute alcohol in pale yellow star-like aggregates, m. p. 124.5°. (Found: N=13.38. $C_{23}H_{24}N_4S_2$ requires N=13.34 per cent.)

trans-p-Methylphenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate prepared by method (i) or (ii), crystallised from absolute alcohol in sulphur-yellow plates, m. p. 95°. It is easily soluble in acetone, benzene, pyridine and chloroform but only sparingly in ligroin, ether and cold alcohol. (Found: N=8.23. $C_{18}H_{20}ON_2S_2$ requires N=8.14 per cent.)

cis-Phenacyl-methyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate

was obtained by methods (ii) and (iv) as pale yellow, slender needles. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol or ligroin. It was extremely soluble in most other organic media; m. p. 93°. (Found: N=8.85. $C_{18}H_{16}ON_2S_2$ requires N=8.86 per cent.)

cis-Phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate, obtained by methods (iii) and (iv), crystallised in pale yellow, soft needles from ligroin, m. p. 86°. It was easily soluble in most organic media from which attempts to crystallise it were fruitless. (Found: C=61.31; H=4.49. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2S_2$ requires C=61.81; H=4.45 per cent.)

cis-Phenacyl-n-propyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate was obtained by method (iv). From ligroin it separated in pale yellow, silky needles, m. p. 61°. (Found: N=8.28. $C_{18}H_{20}ON_2S_2$ requires N=8.14 per cent.)

The corresponding *benzyl* derivative, crystallised from

ligroin in long, pale yellow needles m. p. 75.° (Found : C = 66.94 ; H = 5.35. C₂₃H₂₀ON₂S₂ requires C = 67.34 ; H = 5.1 per cent.)

ois-p-Methyl-phenacyl-methyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate

prepared by methods (iii) and (iv), from methyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone, crystallised from ligroin in star-like aggregates, m. p. 54°, and was highly soluble in most organic solvents. (Found : N = 8.60. C₁₇H₁₈ON₂S₂ requires N = 8.49 per cent.)

cis-p-Methyl-phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate obtained in an analogous manner formed very pale yellow needles, m. p. 76-77.° It was highly soluble in most organic media. (Found : N = 8.20. C₁₈H₂₀ON₂S₂ requires N = 8.14 per cent.)

2-Methylthiol-4 : 5-diphenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

Methylphenyldithiocarbazinate (2 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of pure pyridine, an equal weight of ω -bromoacetophenone added, and the solution was then boiled for about three minutes. The reaction-mixture was poured into water when an oil separated. The oil was dissolved in hot absolute alcohol and allowed to cool. A pale yellow crystalline precipitate (1.15 g.) was obtained. After two or three recrystallisations from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol, the thiodiazine was obtained as pale yellow, hard prisms, m. p. 180°. It was sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone or benzene but easily in pyridine. (Found:

C=64.42; H=4.66. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2S_2$ requires C=64.43; H=4.70 per cent.)

2-Ethylthiol-4 : 5-diphenyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine was obtained from molecular proportions of ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazine and ω -bromoacetophenone in an analogous manner. It was found to be easily soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide and pyridine and separated from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in pale yellow, transparent prisms, m. p. 150°. (Found: C=65.12; H=5.27. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2S_2$ requires C=65.37; H=5.13 per cent.) The corresponding *n*-propyl- and benzyl-thiolthiodiazines could not be obtained by this method.

Conversion of cis-Phenacyl-methyl-phenyldithiocarbazine into 2-Methylthiol-4:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

(a) One gm. of the *cis*-compound in 25 c.c. of absolute alcohol was heated in a sealed tube for four hours at about 100°. The cold alcoholic solution slowly deposited pale yellow crystals of the thiodiazine which, when purified, melted at 180°. A mixture of this compound and that obtained by the previous method had the same melting point. The corresponding *trans*-compound, under the same conditions, also underwent conversion into the same thiodiazine.

(b) The condensation was also effected by heating the *cis*- or *trans*-compound for 15-20 minutes at 140-45°. Water was eliminated; a little sulphuretted hydrogen was also noticed. The pasty mass was dissolved in a small quantity of pyridine, diluted with a large excess of alcohol and set aside for several days. The thiodiazine crystallised out very slowly in transparent prisms which were purified by repeated recrystallisation from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol. The pure product melted at 179-80° and its identity with 2-methylthiol-4:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine was established by the usual methods.

2-Ethylthiol-4:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine was similarly obtained from *cis*- and *trans*-phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazinate.

2-n-Propylthiol-4:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine was prepared according to the method (b) given above. It separated from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in almost white microscopic needles, m. p. 150-151°. (Found: C=66.24; H=6.07. C₁₈H₁₈N₂S₂ requires C=66.27; H=5.52 per cent.)

2-Methylthiol-4-phenyl-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine was obtained from *trans*-p-methylphenacyl-methylphenyldithiocarbazinate by method (a). It crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in golden yellow, shining plates, m. p. 187°. (Found: C=65.19; H=5.18. C₁₇H₁₆N₂S₂ requires C=65.37; H=5.13 per cent.) The *cis*-compound, however, when heated at 100° for three hours in alcoholic solution, yielded the corresponding *trans*-isomeride, m. p. 110°. The thiodiazine was not formed.

Isomeric Transformation of p-Methylphenacyl-ethylphenyldithiocarbazinates.

The *cis*-compound (1 g.) dissolved in 25 c.c. of alcohol was heated at 100° for four hours in a sealed tube. On concentration of the solution a mixture of the isomerides was obtained. These were collected, dried in the air and the isomerides separated by taking advantage of the greater solubility of the *cis*-compound in petroleum ether. The *trans*-compound, under similar conditions, alas yielded a mixture of the two isomerides. Evidently the reaction is reversible, thus:

At a higher temperature (120-30°) intramolecular condensation took place with the formation of 2-ethylthiol-4-phenyl-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine. The thiodiazine

crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in pale yellow, compact needles or prisms, m. p. 148°. (Found: C = 66.11; H = 5.65. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2S_2$ requires C = 66.27; H = 5.52 per cent.)

Constitution of the Isomerides of Phenacyl-ethyl-phenyl-dithiocarbazine.

cis-Phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazine (0.4 g.) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of anhydrous benzene. A little anhydrous copper sulphate was added and the mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature. The copper sulphate gradually turned brown and ultimately black due to the formation of cupric sulphide. After 48 hours the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated. The dark coloured oil left behind was washed with ligroin. It hardened in the course of several hours and was twice recrystallised from a mixture of pyridine and absolute alcohol. The product, pale yellow needles m. p. 150°, was found to be identical with 2-ethylthiol-4:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (*vide* p. 210). The yield was about 45 per cent.

trans-Phenacyl-ethyl-phenyldithiocarbazine, under similar conditions, gave, after removal of benzene, a mixture of the original compound together with a little of the *cis*-isomeride. There was practically no improvement even when the solution was allowed to stand for a week.

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